

**METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING THE FLEXIBILITY OF YOUNG JUDO
ATHLETES**

Otabek Toshmurodov¹, Tehron Erkinov²

¹Sharof Rashidov Samarkand State University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

²Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Corresponding author: Otabek Toshmurodov, e-mail: otoshmurodov74@mail.ru

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Abstract

This article examines the issues of developing the flexibility of young judo athletes on both scientific and practical grounds. During the study, flexibility indicators of 24 judo athletes aged 9–10 were assessed using special control tests. A modern methodology for developing flexibility was devised, and a corresponding set of exercises was created. The results demonstrated the effectiveness of the methodology by analyzing differences between the control and experimental groups. It was noted that this methodology plays an important role in enhancing the athletes' technical readiness and preventing injuries. Judo is a sport that embodies the main components of physical fitness, with flexibility considered one of the most important physical qualities. In order for judo athletes to perform complex technical techniques during competitions, a high level of joint mobility and muscle elasticity is required. This article presents a description of the specially developed methodology for increasing the flexibility of young judo athletes and the results of the research.

Keywords: judo, flexibility, special control tests, sports methodology, competition preparation.

The purpose of our research was to improve the level of flexibility development among young judoka.

Hypothesis: Flexibility determines the level of sportsmanship in judo wrestling. Insufficient development of flexibility, in our opinion, slows down the process of mastering motor skills, cannot reveal the activity of speed, strength, coordination abilities, and also restricts movement, reducing the productivity of physical labor, leading to muscle injuries. But the scientific rationale for this

process is not sufficiently reflected in the scientific literature.

Introduction

Judo is a sport in which continuous and rapid changes during competition place high demands on athletes' physical qualities, including general endurance, speed, and strength, and particularly on joint mobility and the demonstration of flexibility (Casals et al., 2017). These qualities enable athletes to find correct solutions at various stages of a match (Kerimov et al., 2023). Judo fully satisfies a person's natural aspirations to display strength, agility, bravery, resourcefulness, and to stand against evil and violence (Junior et al., 2024). Judo is not merely a sport; it is also a means of achieving physical and moral development. Engaging in judo plays an important role in improving a person's general health, ensuring physical development, and shaping psychological qualities. This activity also contributes to the development of personal character, strengthens self-confidence, and fosters important moral virtues such as courage, determination, honesty, righteousness, bravery, and integrity (Miarka et al., 2000).

As a tool of physical education, judo is distinguished by its universality, since it is not based solely on physical strength but also fosters an individual's ability to quickly and accurately assess situations, make swift decisions, and choose the right course of action (defend, absorb a strike, or counterattack). This process, in turn, sets judo apart as a sport that requires not only physical activity but also an intelligent and strategic approach (Falatovics et al., 2023).

The problem of training judo athletes has been one of the pressing issues extensively studied by the scientific community for many years. Many scientific and methodological works and research have been conducted on this topic. Nevertheless, the relevance of teaching and training in judo has not diminished (Kunzszabo et al., 2024).

In sports-including judo-the process of warming up the body is aimed at improving overall performance by preparing for upcoming physical activities and optimizing vegetative functions (Akbaş et al., 2022). It involves a specially selected set of physical exercises designed to intensify muscle activity and enhance their work capacity, which is particularly significant for the muscles involved (Ambrozy et al., 2022). An increase in body temperature and the temperature of the muscles (especially those prepared for activity) noticeably improves their elasticity and enhances their stretching properties. This, in turn, enables muscles to move with a maximal range of motion and withstand variable loads. In addition, warming up the muscular system is essential for effectively managing energy expenditure and boosting the overall efficiency of physical activity (Kons et al., 2024).

Hypothesis: Flexibility determines the level of sportsmanship in judo wrestling. Insufficient development of flexibility, in our opinion, slows down the process of mastering motor skills, cannot

reveal the activity of speed, strength, coordination abilities, and also restricts movement, reducing the productivity of physical labor, leading to muscle injuries. But the scientific rationale for this process is not sufficiently reflected in the scientific literature.

Methods

24 young judoka aged 9-10 years were analyzed. They were divided into control and experimental groups. Each group consists of 12 people and is distributed equally. At the beginning of the study, their flexibility levels were measured using special control tests presented in table 1 below.

Table 1. Control exercises (tests) used to determine the level of flexibility development in judo athletes

T/r	Control exercises	Exercise content	Evaluation indicators
1	Moving forward and backward in a bridge position (most) (30 s.)	In this exercise, while moving forward, the chin is used, and while moving backward, the shoulder blades are engaged gilamga tekkizish kerak	18 times
2	Running in a circular motion in a bridge position (30 seconds)	While keeping the head and hands on the ground, the legs must rotate around the central axis of the head.	14 times
3	Holding a static position in a bridge posture	In this exercise, one must push forward with the legs as much as possible, touch the mat with the chin, and keep the stomach directed upward	30 seconds
4	Stepping jumps in a bridge position (30 seconds)	In a bridge position, during stepping jumps forward and backward around the central axis of the head, the hands and head must not lift off the ground.	15 times
5	Holding a 90° static position while hanging on a horizontal bar	When holding the legs at a 90° angle, the knees must not bend.	25 seconds
6	Leaning forward from a gymnastics bench without bending the knees (cm)	In this exercise, the knees must not bend (measured from below the feet, in cm).	12 cm

According to the received data, in the bridge position forward and backward movement test (most) for 30 seconds, at the start of the study, the experimental group achieved an average time of 15.9 ± 1.2 seconds, while the control group recorded 16.1 ± 1.6 seconds. The comparison of the indicators showed $t=0.6$; $P>0.05$, indicating no statistically significant differences.

Under the control norms at the beginning of the study, for running in a circle in a bridge position (30 s.), the experimental group showed 10.5 ± 1.1 seconds, while the control group had 10.7 ± 0.9 seconds. The difference between these indicators was $t=0.9$; $P>0.05$; no statistically significant difference was observed.

Table-2. Analysis of flexibility development indicators in 9–10-year-old judo athletes (n=24)

T/r	Control exercises	At the beginning of the study				t	P
		Experimental group		Control group			
		$(\bar{X} \pm \sigma)$	V	$(\bar{X} \pm \sigma)$	V		
1	Forward and backward movement in a bridge position (most) (30 seconds)	$15,9 \pm 1,2$	7,8	$16,1 \pm 1,6$	9,8	0,6	$P>0,05$
2	Running in a circle in a bridge position (30 seconds)	$10,5 \pm 1,1$	10,3	$10,7 \pm 0,9$	8,9	0,9	$P>0,05$
3	Holding a static position in a bridge posture	$12,8 \pm 1,4$	10,9	$12,5 \pm 1,4$	11,6	0,8	$P>0,05$
4	Stepping jumps in a bridge position (30 seconds)	$15,8 \pm 0,9$	5,9	$16,2 \pm 0,8$	5,3	1,6	$P>0,05$
5	Holding a 90° static position while hanging on a horizontal bar	$11,2 \pm 1,3$	11,4	$11,6 \pm 0,9$	8,4	1,3	$P>0,05$
6	Leaning forward from a gymnastics bench without bending the knees (cm)	$10,2 \pm 1,4$	11,8	$10,9 \pm 1,3$	12,1	1,8	$P>0,05$

Under the control norms at the beginning of the study, for holding a static position in a bridge posture, the experimental group recorded 12.8 ± 1.4 seconds, whereas the control group had

12.5±1.4 seconds. The difference between these indicators was $t=0.8$; $P>0.05$; no statistically significant difference was observed.

Under the control norms at the beginning of the study, for stepping jumps in a bridge position (30 s.), the experimental group achieved 15.8±0.9 seconds, while the control group recorded 16.2±0.8 seconds. The difference between these indicators was $t=1.6$; $P>0.05$; no statistically significant difference was observed.

Under the control norms at the beginning of the study, for holding a 90° static position while hanging on a horizontal bar, the experimental group recorded 11.2±1.3 seconds, while the control group had 11.6±0.9 seconds. The difference between these indicators was $t=1.3$; $P>0.05$; no statistically significant difference was observed.

Under the control norms at the beginning of the study, for leaning forward from a gymnastics bench without bending the knees (cm), the experimental group showed 10.2±1.4 seconds, while the control group recorded 10.9±1.3 seconds. The difference between these indicators was $t=1.8$; $P>0.05$; no statistically significant difference was observed.

Flexibility is the main physical quality in judo wrestling, and the effectiveness of training and competition depends on their development. In accordance with the fact that flexibility determines the level of athletic prowess in judo wrestling and in accordance with the objectives of the study, we have developed the following flexibility training method, which includes a set of 6 selected special physical exercises to train flexibility in all parts of the training session.

1. Using repeated spring-like movements.
2. Increasing the intensity of stretching.
3. Performing movements with the maximum range of motion.
4. Utilizing the inertia of a specific part of the body.
5. Using additional external support.
6. Using the active assistance of a partner.

Usually, in the introductory and preparatory parts of a training session – after dynamic physical exercises, when the range of motion gradually increases and depending on the complexity of the physical exercises being performed 7–10 minutes are allocated to flexibility exercises during warm-up. In the main part of the training session, these exercises are done in sets, sequentially for 12–15 minutes, alternating with primary exercises. In the final part of the training session, stretching exercises lasting 7–8 minutes are combined with relaxation exercises.

The judoists participating in the experimental group performed flexibility exercises according to the method developed above for 4 months from september 2024 to december 2024.

Figure 1. A special set of exercises aimed at developing various muscle groups involved in the execution of technical techniques by young judo athletes

Results

The flexibility of the 24 young judoka who participated in the study was reanalyzed at the end of the study. At the same time, the indicators for 6 control exercises performed at the beginning of the study were studied (see Table 3).

According to the control norm at the end of the study, for forward and backward movement in a bridge position (most) (30 s.), the experimental group achieved 17.5 ± 1.1 seconds, while the control group recorded 16.5 ± 1.4 seconds. The difference between the indicators was $t=2.7$; $P<0.05$, indicating statistically significant differences.

According to the control norm at the end of the study, for running in a circle in a bridge position (30 s.), the experimental group recorded 12.1 ± 1.6 seconds, while the control group had 11.2 ± 0.9 seconds. The difference between the indicators was $t=2.4$; $P<0.05$, indicating statistically significant differences.

According to the control norm at the end of the study, for holding a static position in a bridge posture, the experimental group recorded 14.4 ± 2.1 seconds, while the control group had 13.1 ± 1.6 seconds. The difference between the indicators was $t=2.3$; $P<0.05$, indicating statistically significant differences.

3-Table. Analysis of flexibility development indicators in 9–10-year-old judo athletes (n=24)

T/r	Control exercises	At the end of the study				t	P
		Experimental group		Control group			
		($\bar{X} \pm \sigma$)	V	($\bar{X} \pm \sigma$)	V		
1	Forward and backward movement in a bridge position (most) (30 seconds)	17,5±1,1	6,1	16,5±1,4	8,7	2,7	P<0,05
2	Running in a circle in a bridge position (30 seconds)	12,1±1,6	13,1	11,2±0,9	8,5	2,4	P<0,05
3	Holding a static position in a bridge posture	14,4±2,1	14,1	13,1±1,6	12,1	2,3	P<0,05
4	Stepping jumps in a bridge position (30 seconds)	17,5±1,4	7,9	16,6±0,9	5,9	2,4	P<0,05
5	Holding a 90° static position while hanging on a horizontal bar	13,3±1,8	13,6	12,1±1,7	14,3	2,2	P<0,05
6	Leaning forward from a gymnastics bench without bending the knees (cm)	13,5±1,5	11,2	11,7±1,6	14,1	3,8	P<0,001

According to the control norm at the end of the study, for stepping jumps in a bridge position (30 s.), the experimental group achieved 17.5±1.4 seconds, while the control group recorded 16.6±0.9 seconds. The difference between the indicators was t=2.4; P<0.05, indicating statistically significant differences.

According to the control norm at the end of the study, for holding a 90° static position while hanging on a horizontal bar, the experimental group showed 13.3±1.8 seconds, while the control group had 12.1±1.7 seconds. The difference between the indicators was t=2.2; P<0.05, indicating statistically significant differences.

According to the control norm at the end of the study, for leaning forward from a gymnastics bench without bending the knees (cm), the experimental group recorded 13.5±1.5 seconds, while the control group had 11.7±1.6 seconds. The difference between the indicators was t=3.8; P<0.001, indicating statistically significant differences.

Figure 2. Dynamics of flexibility development in judoists aged 9-10 years at the end of the study in %

Discussion

Flexibility exercises should be given after warming up the body, which is achieved through physical exercises with a relatively high load. The same effect can be obtained in a steam bath. The appearance of sweat indicates that the most favorable position has been reached for performing exercises related to stretching muscles. Alternatively, it should be borne in mind that performing high-amplitude exercises in a position where the muscles are less elastic can lead to injury, even if the exercises are performed with normal amplitude (Baudry et al., 2009).

Exercises performed for the purpose of developing flexibility should be included in various stages of training, namely in the preparatory, main and final parts. Optimally, this set of exercises should include 6-8 movements (Franchini et al., 2013). Exercises related to vital movements necessary for the development of joint movements are important for increasing joint activity. It should be borne in mind that performing muscle stretching exercises twice a day (morning and evening) significantly increases physical performance. To bring the level of movement in the joints of the body to a high level, it is recommended to exercise 3-4 times a week (Baić et al., 2022). The number of repetitions of exercises should also be adjusted depending on the size of the muscle groups, the duration of stretching, as well as the age, gender and level of training of the student.

Due to the peculiarities of the quality of flexibility in judo wrestling, special attention is paid to the performance of the wrestling bridge exercise in training, in which the carpet touches only the hands, forehead, sometimes chin and heel, and the back is bent like a bow (Saraiva et al., 2014).

According to the results of our study, the judoists of the experimental group showed a more pronounced development of flexibility qualities compared to the judoists of the control group. There was a particularly noticeable increase in the forward bending exercise from the gymnastic bench without bending the knees (see), where the judoists of the experimental group recorded an increase of 24.4% compared to the beginning of the study.

Conclusion

A comparative analysis of the results showed that, by the end of the experiment, the judo athletes in the experimental group demonstrated greater increases in the studied indicators compared to the control group. The positive dynamics of the research results confirms our hypothesis.

An analysis of the repeated assessments of the flexibility development level in 9–10-year-old judo athletes within the initial training group revealed that, in all control exercises, they achieved noticeably higher results. This indicates the positive effect of the methodology we propose for developing flexibility and demonstrates that it can be used in the training of young judo athletes.

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